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Piano

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Bach, Beethoven & Bowie

The Challenges of the Crossover Keyboardist

By Mike Garson

Mike Garson (left) and flutist Jim Walker with their quartet Free Flight.

Although I'm not a household name, I'm known in the music world, and I believe I'm well respected by those who know me and my art. I've been playing the piano 43 years. I started at seven, and still find it an adventure each time I play. I love the piano. It has, and will always be, a passion of mine. I've worked in many areas of music—classical, pop, jazz, and rock 'n roll. This seems eclectic, but I love music whatever the form. The truth is that I love a portion of each of the above styles, and I do have standards.

I've had the privilege of teaching more than 1,000 piano students. I teach primarily on a private level in addition to giving clinics at various universities around the country. I adore teaching and

being able to give back, much as my teachers did for me. I've found I have always learned from every student as much as I have taught. I've composed since I was 14, and have written more than 1,800 works of all types. Composing is a gift, and I feel blessed to be an artist who has this ability.

Improvisation is another area that I've worked in most of my life. Jazz has been at the base of that. I had the opportunity and privilege to study with many fantastic teachers—Leonard Eisner, Lennie Tristano, Hal Overton, Robert Starer, Herbie Hancock, and Bill Evans, to name a few. Each was an inspiration and served a purpose at the time. Of course, the time comes to abandon all teachers and take the "driver's seat" once and for all. That's

a scary time because one must start the search for one's own voice.

For me, it took quite some time to find myself amid all the piano giants in classical and jazz, no less the great composers of the last four hundred years. That little persistent thought regarding finding my own style and essence never faded, continuing an upward spiral toward that goal. Some people hit it immediately but, in my case, I loved all the greats so much I put myself through years of imitation. While I don't regret this, it might have gone on ten years too long.

When we discussed the directions this article might take, it was suggested that I write about my role as an ensemble player. Prior to that it hadn't dawned on me that this was something I actually do a lot. The term "ensemble playing" always made me think of piano in a chamber group setting. I've done a bit of that, but not nearly as much as I've worked in other groups, from duos to full orchestras. I've also had my solo career, so I never thought of myself as an ensemble player *per se*.

My first quartet (at 14) was called *The Impromptu Quartet*. I still love that name. Dave Liebman, the great sax player, was one of the group. Bass, drums, and myself on piano comprised the rest. We did a recording of two songs ("It Ain't Necessarily So" and "Quiet Village"), and it was pretty good. It was in my first group that I started to learn how to accompany or "comp" (as we say in the jazz world) behind a horn player. This is an art in itself. Filling the spaces, leaving spaces, echoing phrases, countering melodies, harmonizing melodies, stabbing rhythms at certain times are all part of comping. When *not* to play might be more important than when to play. Experiment and experience generally leads you to the proper amount of comping. "Less is more" is probably a good starting point. Over-comping clutters the music and doesn't allow the music to breathe. For many years I didn't like comping, and I always waited for my solo. As the years progressed, I started to like the effects you can create as an accompanist. I prefer to write my own comping. Even Bach used figured bass but allowed room for the clavichord or harpsichord player to do his thing within the rules of the music.

When you join a group, you become a group member. There are certain rules,

some stated and many unstated, that have to be adhered to in order to function in that group. What are some of these rules? First of all, I think parking your ego at the door before entering is a good start. Knowing the common goal of the group is important. Lots of individual practice, in addition to group practice, is also necessary. When to support and when to lead, and the correct balance of the two, can be tricky, but it is vital. Listening—such a simple word and concept—is a crucial attribute. The desire to have the *group* sound great seems obvious, but it is often forgotten. Simple good manners go a long way (in addition to having your craft down). Hopefully, you also love the music you are playing, which transmits the best intention and communication.

After *The Impromptu Quartet*, I played in the high school orchestra (not so easy with all the out-of-tune instruments) and performed with many bands in the Catskill Mountains, size varying in from two to nine pieces. It was a great experience accompanying hundreds of singers each summer—mostly bad singers, but also some greats. Where else can you back Mel Torme, Jackie Mason, Hines, Hines & Dad (Gregory Hines and family) and the local “talent” in one summer? Each required very good sight reading skills and “presence.” Focus and attention “in the moment” were vital. There was little rehearsal time, and scant tolerance from the headliner. This was wonderful training ground, and fun, for a high-school teen.

In order to be an accompanist, you must be able to read chord charts, an acquired craft necessary in the pop and jazz fields. Reading chord symbols and knowing how to voice chords are all part of this skill. In the 1950s and 60s, this knowledge was “underground,” and it was passed on from musician to musician. One of the problems with the jazz world was that much of the data (lines, jazz voicing, comping, phrasing, and so on) was kept secret until the mid-60s. Whether or not that was intentional we’ll never know, but it prevented many musicians from learning this art form. Fortunately, books, videos, and data are now available for anyone who wants to learn. Of course, “feeling” and “living” the music are still the basis.

There are two great artists I have

For me, it took quite some time to find myself amid all the piano giants in classical and jazz, no less the great composers of the last 400 years.

worked with in the context of duet playing. One is Jim Walker, a flutist extraordinaire and my partner in the group *Free Flight*. The other is Eddie Daniels, a phenomenal clarinetist. Jim and I have done many concerts both as part of the group *Free Flight* and as a duet. For 15 years Jim played first flute in two major orchestras (the Pittsburgh Symphony and the Los Angeles Philharmonic). We have played classical, jazz, and new age music together. Accompanying a flute usually requires the use of the soft pedal. (Jim, however, has been known to drown me out, as he can be the loudest flute player in the world!) In playing a jazz duet, there is a lot of interplay between the soloists. The accompanist is more featured than in larger groups, and you can’t depend on the bass and drums for rhythmical support. It’s up to you to create it.

This is where the subject of *illusion* comes in; you need to give the impression that many things are going on that aren’t. Space plays an important role; what you *don’t* play is as important as what you do play. The rests and spaces need to be full of

impulse and intention, not nothingness. The spaces are part of the music, so you must create these too. You can’t let your mind drift, or the music will lose its momentum and impact. It can become boring, and the audience will feel it even though they may not understand the mechanics. Jim and I play lots of notes together, but even between each sixteenth-note is a space to be respected and realized. Practicing this in slow motion is a good drill to learn the technique.

In order to play great in a duet context, much individual practice is necessary. Being familiar with the music before practice allows you to get beyond the notes and convey more emotion and feeling. Again, I bring up listening because it’s the number one factor that often gets overlooked. If you can picture yourself in the audience, instead of at the piano, perhaps you will “hear” it better. Try that as an exercise.

Playing with a beautiful touch is of utmost importance, and getting used to each piano you encounter is crucial. Making the most of each piano is an important factor because there’s nothing you can do to change the instrument. So it pays to accept the instrument and know how to make it work for you. For any live performance, I advise you to have a written agreement stating specifications of the piano (size, condition, tuning availability, and so forth). Even so, try not to let your expectations get too high, because the agreement is not always possible or honored. What you are given is what there is, so my suggestion—and what I have always done—is to let it go and make the best of it. Your performance is still the most important part.

Playing with Eddie Daniels is a wild experience because we both share many similar ideas regarding virtuosity. That can lead to problems, or be the most ecstatic experience if we both stay in the moment. I come back to certain basic principles. Being “in the now” or present time is essential. If your mind is somewhere else, then the time or rhythm will lose its magic. Years of experience have led me to this conclusion. “Being there,” “alertness,” “focus,” and “paying attention,” are all part of this principle. When the soloist is playing lots of notes, generally it’s good for the accompanist to play less. You can

violate this rule, but you'd better be pretty sharp since it can lead to musical catastrophe. Fewer notes in the voicings are always effective during streams of notes from the soloist. With the piano, where you "orchestrate" your coupling and ranges is crucial to making the music feel right. Balancing that with the ranges the soloist is playing in is fun and can be very interesting and creative.

Backing up a singer is a whole course in itself. The first rule is to stay out of the way, and yet be a cushion and very supportive; otherwise the singer will want to kill you. They are a breed unto themselves. They have a definite idea of how they want their music to sound, and how they want to be accompanied. Of course, playing certain inspiring licks, phrases, or rhythms can really help the singer. Consider adding some magic, rather than being too bland. The two-way interchange between yourself and the vocalist can be special when all the basics are in place because it then becomes co-creating—and that leads to its own joy and magic.

Music deals with the subject of aesthetics, and aesthetics is the subject of beauty. That puts you in a special category when you perform. That special place is a different wave-length than normal day-to-day communication, so it is necessary to honor that. This is one of the reasons you must really have your craft down so you can flow and be in that "other stream." It can be wonderful, especially when you don't force it.

Playing in a quartet such as *Free Flight* (I have been part of the group for the last 12 years) can be an amazing experience. *Free Flight* was founded by Jim Walker, and now Jim and I co-lead the group with bass and drums. Sometimes I add synthesizers in addition to the piano. The group utilizes both the classical vocabulary and the jazz idiom. There's no resting on laurels in this group because the amount of technique required is substantial. It is also demanding musically since the repertoire goes from Prokofiev, to the Beatles, to Bach, to Brubeck, to Beethoven, and to Garson. I've been the main composer in the group, and it has been a wonderful outlet for many of my compositions. (I still have a concerto in mind for the group with orchestra.) The group requires much alertness and listening (as I've stated before) plus much inter-

action between the flute and piano. At times, sparse comping to very busy parts requires a great deal of individual practice. For example, when we perform the *Waldstein Sonata*, I don't play it note for note, so I need a lot of personal practice before we release it with the group. The third movement of Prokofiev's *Piano Sonata #7* (in 7/4) needs countless hours before rehearsal with the band. Everyone has to listen very carefully to get a real ensemble effect; dynamics are crucial on the part all members.

Regarding drummers: if they are good, they push me to really work at aspects of my rhythm as that's most of what they practice, and only a portion of what the pianist practices. Since the piano is a percussion instrument, this requires that you continuously improve your rhythmic precision. Utilizing the metronome on two and four (like the Hi Hat of the drums) is a good practice technique, both at a slow tempo and quite fast. Making sure the drums don't overpower the band is a task in itself, and this requires great discipline since drummers generally like to play hard. Playing with an acoustic bass is also wonderful so long as you don't cover up the bass notes in the left hand, or get in the way of this register. In all types of ensemble playing, the same basics apply. Courtesy is crucial for the band's survival. Music is a give-and-take activity. There are times when you are the soloist, and times when you are the support or background. Both are important, and each has its own ethic.

A very special artist I worked with in the '70s, and now again in the '90s, is David Bowie. In fact, I wrote this while touring with him in Europe. Although he did not receive formal conventional training as a musician, as I did, this man is truly a genius. His concept of textures and form is unique, and the type of musicians he chooses is unusual and exceptional. He has a wonderful voice, and accompanying him requires great insight and a tendency towards freedom and living on the edge. His music has many layers. Finding the right spots to fit the piano in is very challenging. The "Alladin Sane" record of 1972 and the "Outside" record of 1995 both have a lot of piano playing. You'll notice I use many 20th-century devices. On these CDs, I called on all my advanced classi-

cal training and knowledge of Ives, Bartók, Haydn, Stravinsky, and so on, as well as the jazz influences of McCoy Tyner and Cecil Taylor.

I mentioned at the outset that I was not a household name. The pluses and minuses of being a relative "unknown" deserve some elaboration. Although you might not be a "star" or make millions, you can still be an artist and share your talent and passion with the world. Fame can be addictive, and can take one off his purpose or mission in life. Fame can also fixate attention on yourself and your identity; you can become excessively self-indulgent and/or self-important. The down side to all this is that the art and music suffer, and your ego grows out of proportion. It's possible that your original intention to share your art with the world gets lost in the power-struggle game of "me, me, me." Some artists manage to stay humble and keep their art pure and clean, but the temptations built into the world of "look how good I am" deemphasize the original intention of the music.

This is not to say that one shouldn't be proud of one's creations (or know that one is very good at what one does), but this is a warning that the downward spiral of fame and self-importance can be very distressing to the artist. Whereas when one communicates the true essence of the music and lets it reveal real love and happiness, and even the darker sides of life, the rewards of giving lead to true self-satisfaction.

I'm not trying to turn this into a sermon or make art into religion, but there is a fine line between great art and true spirituality (not the conventional organized religion, but true spirituality) because spirituality is truly creative. So music can range from very basic dance music to inspiring works such as Beethoven's *Missa Solemnis*, Verdi's *Requiem*, or Bill Evans' *Peace Piece*. You can choose what it is you want to say with your art and follow through with it. This takes a lot of courage, but what else is there to do in life but follow through on one's own goals and desires? The end result, and the joy while one is creating and working in the art, can be quite fulfilling.

I have stated my own truths and discoveries won through many years of practicing, playing, and performing. They are my reality. If they ring true with you, utilize them. If they don't, try finding your own truths, as that makes for clarity in one's own mind and can lead to a better life—perhaps, ultimately—to a better world. ✚